

The Impact of Financial Transparency on Parental Engagement in Education Financing at Beo Rahong Elementary School

Leonardus W Dino Setiawan, Richardus Nardin *

^{1,2,3} Karya Ruteng College of Economics

1,2,3Jl. Satar Tacik No. 14 Ruteng, Manggarai 86518 East Nusa Tenggara

Correspondence: aldhonempa@gmail.com

Article Info

Submission date:

Accepted date:

Keywords:

Transparency;

Parental Participation

Keywords:

Financial Transparency;

Parental Participation

ISSN (print):

ISSN (online):

Abstract

Financial transparency is a practice whereby educational institutions, such as schools, clearly and comprehensively disclose their sources of income and expenditure allocations on a regular basis. This study aims to investigate the influence of Institutional Ownership, Audit Quality, and Independent Commissioners on Financial Transparency and its effect on Parental Participation. The population for this study comprises schools and the parents of their students. After conducting a sample selection, 54 respondents were identified for the research using the purposive sampling method. Data analysis for this study was performed using multiple regression methods. The results of the analysis and hypothesis testing indicate that financial transparency positively influences parental participation.

1. Introduction

Education is the main factor in creating quality human resources. To improve the quality of education, the financing aspect cannot be ignored. One of the challenges in managing education funds is financial transparency. Transparency in school financial management reflects openness in conveying information about the income, use, and accountability of the school's funds.

According to Mardiasmo (2009), transparency is openness in providing information related to public resource management activities to parties who need it. Transparency indicators must be met, namely, Informative, Openness, and Disclosure. Informative means providing information flow, news, explanation of mechanisms, procedures, data, and facts to stakeholders who need information clearly and accurately.

With good transparency, parents can understand how funds are being used and feel more motivated to support their children's education. On the contrary, a lack of transparency can lead to misunderstandings,

dissatisfaction, and decreased participation in education financing.

Parental participation in education refers to the active involvement of parents in various aspects of a child's education, both at home and school. This includes the academic, social, and emotional support provided to the child. Participation is the conscious and voluntary involvement of a person or group of people in a particular activity, decision, or process to achieve the common good. According to Ayudia (2014), the participation of parents of students is a form of parental involvement or awareness owned by parents related to the importance of education for their children, especially in terms of solving a problem in the implementation of quality education, related to providing and meeting the needs of the school, both emotionally and materially.

However, in practice, many schools still experience obstacles in implementing financial transparency. This is evidenced by the 2022 Indonesia *Corruption Watch* (ICW) survey, which shows that only around 30% of schools actively publish their financial statements to the public. In addition, the 2023 Financial Audit Agency report revealed various irregularities in

Received: 15 August 2025

Revised: 18 August 2025

Accepted: 22 August 2025

Copyright © authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17018582>

managing the BOS Fund, including inaccurate reporting and the use of funds that were not designated. Similar problems were also detected by the Ombudsman of the Republic of Indonesia, who noted that most of the complaints from the public in the education sector are related to the non-disclosure of school financial information.

Several factors, such as the lack of a clear reporting system, the lack of communication between schools and parents, and low awareness of the importance of transparency, often motivate parental involvement in education financing. Parents often hesitate to make additional contributions if there are no transparent reports on managing school funds.

At SDK Beo Rahong, the lack of parental participation in education financing is still a challenge. This raises the question of the extent to which financial transparency implemented by schools affects parents' attitudes and participation in supporting education financing activities. Therefore, this study is important to analyze how the financial transparency implemented in the Beo Rahong SDK affects parental participation in supporting education financing.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Financial Transparency

Transparency is something real, clear, open, and accountable to other parties or the public interested in what has been done. According to Hasibuan (2021), financial transparency is very important to increase the support of parents, the community, and the government in implementing all school educational programs. Transparency can also create a sense of mutual trust between parties, for example, between the government, the community, parents, and school residents, by providing information and ensuring easy access to accurate and complete information.

Forms of Financial Transparency

According to Krisna (2003), the forms of transparency are:

- a. Provision of clear information about procedures, costs, and responsibilities. Financial transparency through clear information about procedures, costs, and responsibilities in education means that every aspect of fund management must be open and easily accessible to stakeholders, such as students, parents, teachers, and the community.
- ❖ Ease of access to information. Ease of access to information in financial transparency means that all information related to budgets, expenditures, and financial statements must be available and easily accessible to interested parties. In the context of

public or educational institutions, ease of access to information allows parents, students, and the public to know how funds are being used, whether they are being used for planning, and whether there are any irregularities. With easy and clear access, transparency is maintained, public trust increases, and the opportunity for financial abuse can be minimized.

- ❖ Develop a complaint mechanism. The complaint mechanism in financial transparency aims to provide an official channel for the public or interested parties to report non-conformities, abuses, or ambiguities in fund management. This mechanism can be a suggestion box, hotline, digital platform, or discussion forum that allows the public to submit complaints and get a quick and appropriate response. With this mechanism, transparency can be better maintained because every financial problem can be monitored and followed up properly.
- ❖ Increase the flow of information. Improving the flow of information in financial transparency means ensuring that financial data and reports are disseminated quickly, clearly, and easily understood by all stakeholders. Financial information should be updated regularly and available in various formats, such as annual reports, infographics, or online publications, to be accessible to the wider public. With a good flow of information, stakeholders can better understand and supervise the use of funds, thereby preventing potential irregularities or inefficiencies in financial management.

Factors Affecting Financial Transparency

According to Masruroh and Praptoyo (2015), the factors that affect financial transparency are:

- a. External Pressure
Pressure from outside parties, such as parents, the government, or supervisory institutions, can encourage educational institutions to be more open in financial management.
- b. Environmental Uncertainty
Uncertainty in the social, economic, and policy environment can affect how institutions manage their finances. In unstable conditions, transparency is a way to maintain trust and create a sense of security for parents and the community towards the sustainability of education services.
- c. Management Commitment

The commitment of the Principal and management plays an important role in

creating a transparent financial system. Management with integrity and high awareness of the importance of accountability will strive to prepare financial statements openly, involve parents in evaluations, and submit financial information regularly.

d. Resource Capacity

The limitation or adequacy of resources, such as competent administrative personnel, financial information systems, and other supporting facilities, greatly affects the implementation of financial transparency. Institutions with adequate resources will find it easier to compile, manage, and submit financial reports appropriately and accurately.

Financial Transparency Indicators

Mardiasmo (2009) stated that the indicators of transparency are:

a) Informative

This takes the form of providing information flow, news, explanations of mechanisms, procedures, data, and facts to stakeholders who need information clearly and accurately.

b) Openness

Public information disclosure gives everyone the right to obtain information, knowing that all public information must be open and accessible to every user, apart from the excluded information regulated by the law.

c) Disclosure

In the form of disclosure to the public or the public (*stakeholders*) on financial activities and performance.

Parental Participation

Parental participation is active involvement in children's development and education in the home and school environment. This form of involvement can include support in learning, guidance in forming character, and creation of an environment conducive to their growth and development. According to Slameto (2015), parental participation is the active involvement of a person or a group of people consciously contributing voluntarily to school development programs and being involved in planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation.

Form of Parental Participation

Dwiningrum (2011) stated that there are two forms of participation.

1. Physical participation.

Physical participation is a form of participation that relates to a tangible contribution made in the form of funds, facilities, or other resources. This form of participation greatly influences the continuity of

teaching and learning activities, especially in the provision of adequate educational facilities and infrastructure.

One of the main forms of physical participation is the payment of tuition. This fee can be tuition fees (Education Development Contributions) at formal schools, voluntary donations, or other educational expenses. These payments help the school's day-to-day operations, including teacher salaries, facility maintenance, and the procurement of learning tools. Material participation can also be realized in the form of providing learning tools for children. Parents play a role in meeting children's needs, such as buying books, school uniforms, stationery, and other educational equipment. The availability of this equipment helps children learn more optimally and increases their comfort in participating in academic activities.

In addition to money, physical participation also includes community service activities or cooperation to reduce school operational costs. For example, parents can help repair school buildings, create additional facilities such as reading gardens, or procure sports equipment. This collaboration allows schools to save budgets and allocate funds for other, more urgent needs.

2. Non-Physical Participation

In addition to contributions in the form of funds or materials, parental participation can also include moral, intellectual, and financial involvement in educational financial management. This non-physical participation is often not directly visible, but it has a major impact on the effectiveness of education financing systems.

The main form of non-physical participation is participation in decision-making related to education financing. Parents can participate in school committee meetings or discussions with the school to determine funding allocation, budget transparency, and other financing policies. With this involvement, education funds can be managed more transparently and according to the main needs of the school. Another support included in non-physical participation is the empowerment of the family economy to support the child's education. Parents with economic limitations may seek additional employment opportunities, participate in financial management programs, or participate in creative economy activities to help them finance their child's education without relying too heavily on external assistance.

Factors Affecting Parental Participation

According to Patmonodewo (2003), the involvement of parents in education in schools is influenced by three levels of readiness, namely:

- a. Teacher attitude, readiness, and skills are essential because teachers create an environment that encourages parental involvement. Teachers with good communication skills and an open attitude more successfully invite parents to participate.
- b. The readiness of the school or program also affects parental involvement. Schools that have supportive policies, such as regular parent-teacher meetings or parenting seminars, can increase parental involvement. Clear communication and flexibility in involving parents are also supportive factors.
- c. The readiness of parents themselves also determines. Not all parents have the same understanding of their role in a child's education. Factors such as their level of education, economic conditions, and experience with the education system can affect their involvement. Schools can provide education so parents better understand the importance of their role.

Parental Participation Indicators.

According to Utama (2006), the indicators of parental participation in education financing are:

1. Payment of Official School Fees.
Parents show their participation by paying the tuition fees officially set by the school. This fee is usually mandatory and is part of the school's operational funding source.
2. Contributions to the School Committee.
In addition to the mandatory fees, parents are often asked to make donations to the school committee, either voluntarily or as part of school development programs. This contribution reflects parental support for the school committee's policies and activities.
3. Financing of School Physical Facilities.
Schools sometimes require additional parental support to construct or improve facilities, such as teachers' homes, additional classrooms, or sports facilities. Participation in this form shows parents' commitment to improving the quality of the learning environment.
4. Purchase of Student Learning Needs.
Parents actively meet their children's learning needs by purchasing textbooks, stationery, school uniforms, personal desks and chairs (if needed), library supplies, and sports activities. This shows their participation in supporting direct student learning.

5. Student Welfare Financing.

In addition to the academic aspect, parents also finance students' daily needs such as transportation money to school, meal money, and pocket money. This includes participation related to children's welfare while participating in educational activities.

Frame of Mind

Research Hypothesis

According to Mardiasmo (2009), transparency is a principle that guarantees access to or openness of public financial information. If transparency is applied in school financial management, accountability will be created, which has implications for increasing community participation, including students' parents.

By referring to this theory, the hypothesis in this study can be formulated as follows:

- > H1: There is a positive and significant influence of financial transparency on parental participation in education financing at SDK Beo Rahong.
- > Ho: Financial transparency had no significant effect on parental participation in education financing at SDK Beo Rahong.

Types of Research

The type of research used in this study is quantitative research. Quantitative research uses numbers or numerical data to explain, test, or prove a phenomenon. Creswell (2014) emphasizes that quantitative research is a method that focuses on collecting numerical data to test hypotheses objectively. This study aims to help draw conclusions or generalizations of theories.

Research Time and Location

This research was carried out at SDK Beo Rahong, North Rahong District, Manggarai Regency. This location was chosen because it is by the research objectives and relevant to the context of the problem

raised. It is planned to take place from May to June 2025 and cover the stages of preparation, data collection, analysis, and reporting of research results.

Population and sample

- ✓ Population
This study includes all parents or guardians of SDK Beo Rahong students for the 2024/2025 school year, which totals 116 people.
- ✓ Sample
The Number of samples was determined using the Slovin formula, because the population is relatively small (under 10,000 people). The formula used is:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Information:

n = Number of samples
N Total population (116 people)

e = Error rate (0.10 or 10%)

The calculation is as follows:

$$n = \frac{116}{1+116(0,10)^2} = \frac{116}{1+116(0,01)} = \frac{116}{1+1,16} = \frac{116}{2,16} = 53,70$$

Because the Number of samples must be an integer, it is rounded to 54 respondents. Thus, the Number of participants in this study is 54 parents of students.

Variable Operational Definition

Variable Operational Definition

Ye s	Variab le	Definition	Indicators
1	Variable X (Financial Transparency).	Financial transparency is how the school's financial information is open, accessible, and understood by the students' parents. Transparency includes the reporting process, the submission of information, and the involvement of parents in the supervision of the use of education funds.	The following indicators measure this variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informative • Openness • Disclosure
2	Variable Y (Parental Participation)	Parental participation is the involvement	The following indicators measure this variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payment of official school fees

tion in Education Financing).	of parents in supporting the financing of education, both materially and non-materially, which reflects their concern and responsibility for the school's progress.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributions to the school committee • Financing of school physical facilities • Purchase of students' learning needs • Student welfare financing
-------------------------------	---	---

Data Collection Techniques

In this study, data were collected using three techniques, namely questionnaires, interviews, and documentation.

❖ Questionnaire

According to Sujarweni (2020), a questionnaire is a data collection instrument that involves providing several statements or written questions to respondents for them to answer.

The questionnaire obtained quantitative data on financial transparency and parental participation in education financing at SDK Beo Rahong. It is arranged on a Likert scale with five answer choices.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Description of Research Data

a). Variable X (Financial Transparency)

Variable X in this study is Financial Transparency. Data on this variable were collected using a questionnaire technique. The questionnaire used was compiled in the form of a Likert scale with five answer choices, namely: Strongly Agree (SS), Agree (S), Neutral (N), Disagree (TS), Strongly Disagree (STS). This questionnaire was distributed to 54 respondents who were parents of SDK Beo Rahong students. Respondents were asked to provide an assessment according to their experience and perception of the school's financial management openness.

The Number of respondents (N) in this study is 54. The minimum value on the Financial Transparency variable is 34, while the maximum value is 50. The mean of this variable is 44.30, with a standard deviation of 3.780. This shows that the level of financial transparency in schools is in the high category and relatively evenly distributed among respondents because the standard deviation is relatively low.

Meanwhile, the minimum value for the parental participation variable is 29, and the maximum value is 50. The average value for parental participation was 45.56, with a standard deviation of 4.905. This means that the level of parental participation in education financing in schools is also in the high category, but the spread is slightly more varied than for the financial transparency variable.

Overall, both variables have a high average and a fairly controlled data dissemination size, which can support the feasibility of further analysis using inferential statistical tests.

b. Variable y (Participation of people in education financing)

Variable Y in this study focuses on the level of parental participation in supporting education financing at SDK Beo Rahong. Participation is interpreted as voluntary parental involvement in providing financial assistance or other support related to the child's educational needs at school. The measurement of these variables is carried out through ten statements in a questionnaire compiled on the five-point Likert scale, namely:

- 1 = Strongly Disagree (STS)
- 2 = Disagree (TS)
- 3 = Doubt (R)
- 4 = Agree (S)
- 5 = Strongly Agree (SS)

Each item aims to describe a form of parental participation that includes willingness to pay, make voluntary contributions, and be involved in co-financing activities. The following is one of the results of the frequency analysis of respondents' statements regarding participation in education financing:

INTERVIEW RESULTS

Interviews are one of the data collection techniques in this study. Researchers interviewed directly with relevant parties, such as school principals, treasurers, and students' parents. Interview activities were conducted face-to-face in the school environment and at residents' homes, with a relaxed and communicative approach so that respondents felt comfortable providing information.

The interview was semi-structured, meaning that the researcher prepared several main questions but still provided space for the respondents to explain more broadly according to their experience and understanding. It is important to dig into in-depth information related to financial transparency practices in schools and the level of parental participation in education financing. During the interview process, the researcher recorded the conversation's results manually and also recorded important points to maintain the accuracy of the data.

Interview with the Principal

As the main person in charge at SDK Santo Yosef Beo Rahong, the Principal is a key informant in describing financial transparency practices and parental involvement in supporting education financing. In the interview, he explained that school fund management activities are systematically arranged according to priority needs.

According to him, information related to finances is regularly conveyed in official forums such as school committee meetings and student guardian meetings. Financial statements are presented orally and attached in written form so that parents can read and understand them directly. He said:

"Regarding finances, we usually discuss it in meetings with parents. Every semester, we report both orally and in writing. So parents know what the funds are used for."

In addition to submitting reports, the school opens a dialogue room when parents want to ask questions or submit responses. The Principal emphasized the importance of an open attitude in responding to this. He explains:

"We are always open. If parents ask about the report or do not understand, we explain it slowly so everyone can understand."

Regarding the form of parental involvement, he said that participation is not only financial, but also in attendance and support for school activities, such as community service. According to him, information disclosure helps build trust and mutual responsibility. He added:

"Every time there is a meeting with parents, we submit financial reports through presentations. We usually show it through slides, from the details of incoming funds to expenses, such as ATK, facility improvements, or children's activities. We explain them one by one openly so that all parents know where the money is going. If anyone wants to ask a question, we will give time for discussion. So, everyone can see and judge for themselves; nothing is covered up."

At the end of the interview, the Principal expressed his hope that collaboration between schools and parents would continue to be maintained to advance children's education. He stated:

"Our hope for the future is that parents will continue to help the school actively. Because this school is not only the teacher's responsibility but also our collective responsibility."

This interview shows that the Principal applies the principle of financial transparency in real terms in institutional practice. Openness in submitting financial statements and open communication with parents encourage trust and active participation. These findings corroborate the quantitative data that financial transparency contributes to parental participation in education financing.

Interview with the school treasurer

The interview was conducted with SDK Santo Yosef Beo Rahong's Treasurer to obtain in-depth information about the school's financial recording system and the mechanism for delivering financial information to students' parents. In this interview, the resource person explained that the main task of the school treasurer is to record all financial transactions, both income and expenses, as well as compile periodic financial reports to be submitted to the school and parents.

The Treasurer explained that financial statements are generally submitted through official meetings, such as committee meetings or student guardian meetings. In this activity, reports were submitted orally and in the form of written documents distributed to the meeting participants. He said:

"We usually submit financial reports through official meetings, such as committee meetings or student guardian meetings. It is delivered directly and distributed as a PPT at the time of the presentation, so that parents know what the funds are used for."

Regarding parents' understanding of financial statements, the Treasurer said that most parents can understand the information submitted, especially when the report is explained using simple and systematic language. However, not all parents immediately understood the report's content, so the school provided room for discussion and additional explanations. He stated:

"Most parents can understand the report, especially if we explain it simply. However, some do not understand, so we usually explain again and give time to answer."

He also explained that in preparing financial statements, the school deliberately uses terms that are easy to understand so as not to cause confusion among parents. According to him, simplifying the terms and format of reports is a form of school responsibility in building transparent financial communication. In his interview, he mentioned:

"To make it easy to understand, we deliberately use not too complicated terms. So we adjust the report's language so that parents can participate in monitoring and feel involved."

Furthermore, the Treasurer said that the disclosure of financial information positively impacted parental participation. He revealed that parents are more motivated to contribute in the form of funds, goods, and energy. This is reflected in the enthusiasm of parents to support school activities. He added:

"Based on my experience as a treasurer, openness in financial management is very helpful in building parental trust. Whenever I publicly present my financial statements in meetings, parents seem more confident and do not hesitate to participate. Some volunteers provide contributions, help provide school supplies, or go directly when there are activities. They feel more comfortable getting involved as long as they know where the money is going."

From this interview, it can be concluded that the Treasurer has an important role in maintaining transparency in financial management at SDK Santo Yosef Beo Rahong. Financial statements are presented openly in official forums, using simple language to make them easy to understand. This openness has a positive impact on the level of trust and participation of parents in supporting education financing. These results reinforce quantitative findings showing that financial transparency affects parental participation.

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive statistical test

Descriptive statistical analysis was carried out to provide an overview of the research data that had been collected. The main purpose of this analysis is to describe the characteristics of each of the research variables before further analysis, such as classical assumption tests and regression analysis, is carried out. In this study, two main variables are analyzed descriptively, namely Financial Transparency (X) and Parental Participation in Education Financing (Y).

Descriptive statistics present several important measures in the data distribution, namely minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation. The minimum and maximum values provide information about the lower and upper limits of the respondents' scores. Meanwhile, the average value describes the data's central tendency, and the standard deviation indicates the extent to which the data is spread from its average value.

The results of descriptive statistical data processing from 54 respondents using the SPSS program are shown in the following table:

Descriptive Statistical Test Results

	N	Mini mum	Ma xi mu m	Me an	Std. Devi ation
Financial transparency	54	34	50	44.30	3.780
Parental Participation	54	29	50	45.56	4.905
Valid N (listwise)	54				

Classic Assumption Test

Before performing a simple linear regression analysis, a classical assumption test is first performed to ensure that the data meet the requirements or basic assumptions needed in the regression model. The classical assumption tests used in this study include:

A.. Normality Test

The normality test was carried out to determine whether the data in this study were normally distributed. Normal distribution is an important requirement in simple linear regression analysis because the parametric regression model assumes that the residual data have a normal distribution.

In this study, the normality test was carried out using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test with the assistance of the SPSS program. The test results are in Table 4.6.2 below.

Table 4.6.2
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual		
N			54	
Normal Parameters, b	Mean		.0000000	
	Std. Deviation		4.71774814	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute		.089	
	Positive		.051	
	Negative		-.089	
Test Statistic			.089	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c			.200d	
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed) ^e	Sig. 99%	Lower Bound	.338	
		Upper Bound	.362	
	Confidence Interval			

a. Test distribution is Normal.
 b. Calculated from data.
 c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
 d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.
 e. Lilliefors' method based on 10000 Monte Carlo samples with starting seed 299883525.

B. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test was carried out to determine whether the regression model has an inequality of variance from one residual observation to another. A good regression model does not experience symptoms of heteroscedasticity, meaning that residual variance must be constant (homoscedasticity).

In this study, the heteroscedasticity test was carried out by the scatterplot method between the residual value (ZRESID) and the prediction value (ZPRED). The results of the scatterplot are presented in the following image:

Scatterplot Heteroscedasticity Test

It is seen that the data points are randomly scattered around the horizontal axis (value zero on the Y axis) and do not form a specific pattern, such as constriction, spread up/down, or form a specific curve.

The residual distribution does not show a systematic pattern, so it can be concluded that the regression model in this study does not experience symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Thus, the assumption of homocedasticity is met, and the regression model is feasible for analysis.

❖ Interview

Sugiyono (2018) argues that interviews are a data collection technique that can be used to find problems that must be researched. Interviews were conducted semi-structured with school principals and treasurers to obtain more in-depth information about financial transparency practices and the role of parents in financing education. This interview aims to support and enrich the data from the questionnaire.

❖ Documentation.

According to Sugiyono (2018), documentation is a method used to obtain data and information in the form of books, archives, documents, numbers, and drawings in the form of reports and information that can support research.

Documentation is carried out to obtain secondary data such as the Number of students, the

organizational structure of the school committee, school financial statements, and other supporting documents relevant to the research variables.

3.6 Data Analysis Techniques

According to Sugiyono (2018), data analysis techniques involve collecting data from all respondents, grouping them based on criteria, conducting tests on each variable, and presenting data after testing. The data analysis technique in this study was carried out quantitatively through the following stages:

3.6.1 Descriptive statistical analysis

According to Ghozali (2018), descriptive statistical analysis provides an overview of descriptive statistics (mean, variance, maximum, minimum, sum, average, range, kurtosis, and skewness. The goal is to get a general idea of financial transparency and parental participation.

3.6.2 Classical assumption test

According to Purnomo (2017), the classical assumption test is used to determine whether there is residual normality, multicollinearity, autocorrelation, and heteroskedasticity in the regression model. The classic assumption test carried out is as follows:

❖ Normality Test

Sugiyono (2018) states that the normality test determines whether the data is normally distributed. One of the methods used is the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. This test tests whether the distribution of sample data differs significantly from the normal distribution. In this test, the null hypothesis states that the data is normally distributed. If the significance value (p-value) If the result is greater than 0.05, then it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. However, if the p-value is smaller than 0.05, then the data is considered not normally distributed, which can affect the regression analysis results.

❖ Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity is the presence of variance from residual variance for all observations in the regression model. According to Basuki (2015), the heteroscedasticity test is used to determine the existence of deviations from the conditions of classical assumptions in the regression model, where the absence of heteroscedasticity must be met.

3.6.3. Simple Linear Regression Analysis

Sugiyono (2018) states that simple regression is based on one independent variable's functional or causal relationship with one dependent variable. The aim was to test the influence of the financial transparency variable (X) on parental participation (Y) using a simple linear regression technique.

Simple Linear Regression Test A

		Coefficients ^a			t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients			
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.584	3.814		1.727	.090
	transparansi keuangan	.841	.092	.785	9.148	<.001

Based on these results, multiple linear regression equations are obtained as follows:

$$Y = a + bX + e$$

$$Y = 6.854 + 0.841X + e$$

Information:

Y = bound variable (parental participation)

X = independent variable (financial transparency)

a = constant

b = regression coefficient

The test was carried out using the 2022 version of SPSS software.

From the above equation, it can be interpreted that:

- a) The constant value of 6,854 means that if all independent variables (financial transparency) do not change, then the level of parental participation has a positive value of 6,854.
- b) The simple linear regression test resulted in the financial transparency regression coefficient being 0.841. A positive sign means that if the quality perception variable increases, the level of parental participation interest will increase.

REFERENCES

Azkiyah, Z., Fuad, N., & Matin. (2024). *Literature study: School financial transparency on student-parent participation*. Proceedings of the National Seminar on Education, FKIP, University of Lampung, 315–321. <https://ejournal.fkip.unila.ac.id/index.php/prosem/article/view/47>

Ayudia, C. (2014). The Principal's efforts to increase parental participation at SDN North Pariaman District, Pariaman City. *Journal of Education Management*, 2(1). Accessed from <https://ejournal.unp.ac.id/index.php/bahana/article/view/3739>

Basuki, A. T., & Prawoto, N. (2015). *Regression analysis in economics & business research: Equipped with SPSS & EVIEWS applications*. Jakarta: Rajawali Press.

Bahaddur, M. (2012). *Participation of students' parents in learning at Salman Al Farisi Integrated Islamic Elementary School, Yogyakarta* (Thesis, Yogyakarta State University).

- Dwiningrum, S. I. A. (2011). *Decentralization and community participation in education*. Yogyakarta: Student Library.
- Ghozali, I. (2016). *Applications of multivariate analysis with the IBM SPSS 25 program (9th Edition)*. Semarang: Publishing Agency of Diponegoro University.
- Hasibuan, L. (2021). *Managing Tuition Costs: A Literature Study Review*. Journal of Literaology, 5(2), 196–210.
- Indonesia Corruption Watch. (2022). *Portrait of BOS fund transparency in schools: Results of a national survey*. Jakarta: ICW. Accessed from <https://antikorupsi.org>
- Ismail, Y. (2019). *The effect of accountability and transparency in BOS fund management on the participation of student parents at SMA Negeri 1 Luwu Utara (Thesis)*. University of Muhammadiyah Makassar.
- Komba, A. (2014). *The effect of transparency, accountability, and parent participation of students on the effectiveness of the BOSDA program at the junior high school level in the Pamulang District, South Tangerang City (Thesis, Syarif Hidayatullah State Islamic University, Jakarta)*.
- Lukman, A. K. (2023). *The effect of transparency, accountability, and parent participation of students on the effectiveness of the BOSDA program at the junior high school level in Pamulang District, South Tangerang City (Thesis, Syarif Hidayatullah State Islamic University Jakarta)*. <https://repository.uinjkt.ac.id/dspace/handle/123456789/71457>
- Mardiasmo. (2009). *Public sector accounting*. Yogyakarta: No.
- Masrurroh, A. F., & Praptoyo, S. (2015). *Factors that affect the transparency of the city's financial statements*. Journal of Accounting Science & Research, 4(7). <https://jurnalmahasiswa.stiesia.ac.id/index.php/jira/article/view/3554/3569>
- Muhajirin. (2012). *The management of education financing is sourced from community participation*. Journal of Educational Sciences, 41(2), 66–74. <https://doi.org/10.15294/lik.v41i2.2339>
- Nurhayati. (2017). *Theoretical analysis of transparency in regional financial management in Indonesia*. Political Triassic, 1(2). <https://www.journal.unrika.ac.id/index.php/jurnaltriaspolitika/article/download/1062/871>
- Scott, A. Y. (2021). *The effect of accountability, transparency, and parental participation on the effectiveness of BOS fund management in State High Schools in Samarinda City (Thesis, Islamic University of Indonesia)*.
- Patmonodewo, S. (2003). *Early childhood education*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Purnomo, H. (2017). *Introduction to statistics for economics and business*. Yogyakarta: Deepublish.
- Riadi, M. (2021). *Financial transparency*. Accessed from <https://www.kajianpustaka.com/2020/01/transparansi-keuangan.html?m=1>
- Saroso, H. (2020). *Research methodology: Theory and practice*. Yogyakarta: Deepublish.
- Sari, R. A., Siregar, M. F. Z., & Nurhamidah. (2024). *Parental participation in early childhood education*. Cybernetics: Journal of Educational Research and Social Studies, 5(3). <http://pusdikra-publishing.com/index.php/jrss>
- Slameto. (2015). *Learning and Factors Influencing It*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Siregar, O. K., Hasibuan, H. A., & Erhan, A. N. J. (2019). *Accountability and transparency in managing school revenue and expenditure budgets on teacher performance at SMP Negeri 1 Tanjungbalai*. Journal of Business & Public Accounting, 10(1), 57–71.
- Sudarmono, S., Hasibuan, L., & Us, K. A. (2021). *Education financing*. Journal of Islamic Education Management and Strategy (JMPIS), 2(1), 266–279. <https://doi.org/10.38035/jmpis.v2i1>
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Quantitative, qualitative, and R&D research methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sujarweni, V. W. (2020). *Quantitative and qualitative research methods*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Baru Press.
- Sutama. (2006). *Educational Management: Basic Concepts and Principles*. Yogyakarta: Student Library.
- Widyastiti, N. W. (2018). *Community participation in education*. Yogyakarta: Deepublish.
- Widodo, A., Fauzi, R., & Mulyawan, S. (2023). *Educational Financial Management*. Bandung: Widina Bhakti Persada.